

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING THE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

Djurayeva P.S.

National center of training teachers in new methods of Navai region, department " Methods of preschool, primary and special education" associate professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14212359>

Abstract. *This paper discusses the topics on improving the quality of national education by creating an information environment, the importance of higher education institutions, teaching using telecommunication technologies, electronic textbooks and complexes, forming the communicative competence of future primary school specialists through information technologies.*

Keywords: *education system, future primary school specialty, educational goal, information system, information culture, spatial and temporal change of education, mastering algorithms.*

Introduction

The main goal of informatization of education in our republic is to increase the quality of national education by creating a unified educational information environment based on the use of information technologies. One of the complex and important problems of the higher education institution is the optimization of students' future professional skills, improving their professional skills, this task is of particular importance for higher education teachers, in which: it was emphasized that "the main measure for the correct implementation of education reform is the promotion of every citizen of the country with appropriate education and qualifications to the level where he can become a necessary specialist in any country of the world". Due to the goal of harmonizing the education system in our country with the new changes in the world, this makes it mandatory to make changes to the quality of education in the higher educational institutions of our country.

In 2000, as a result of the integration of two important programs in the field of world education ("General Program on News" and "Intergovernmental Program on Informatics"), the program "News for Everybody" was published [2]. In this program, it is emphasized that teaching using information technologies, especially telecommunication technologies, electronic textbooks and complexes has a special place in the educational information system. The conclusion from this is that it is necessary to form professional knowledge and skills in order to find solutions to the problems that arise in the educational process through the use of information technologies in the formation of communicative competence of future specialists. The main direction of formation of communicative competence of the future elementary school specialist through information technologies is characterized by meeting the requirements of modern society, ability to make independent decisions, competitiveness, information, knowledge and skills. Informatization is an organizational, socio-economic, scientific-technical process aimed at the development of electronic resources and information systems based on the use of information technologies [4]. At the same time, informatization is directly related to the pedagogical process, because the information literacy of students forms the competence of their knowledge and skills. It is necessary

to create an opportunity to become the subject of his own actions in the educational process of forming the communicative competence of the future elementary school teacher through information technologies. This, in turn, is primarily the self-education, self-development, improvement of self-knowledge, self-expression, self-control of the future elementary school teacher.

Research materials and methodology

One of the requirements for the formation of communicative competence of a future primary school specialist is the ability to widely use information technologies, to receive quality education from them, and a high level of professional training as a qualified specialist. Communication (lot. *communicatio* — share link, discuss) — 1) participation — 1) method of participation, connection of one part with another part; 2) talk, give information. "Communication mainly performs cognitive functions and is carried out with the help of language" [5]. In the philosophical dictionary it is said: communication - consultation with someone - a category of philosophy that helps the "I" to find itself in another, means communication [6]. The content of information technologies in the formation of the communicative competence of the future specialist through information technologies have taken place in the views of philosophers, psychologists, pedagogues from the earliest times to the present day and are being systematized based on the demands of society. In the works of scientists Hegel, Aristotle, B. Russell, G. Leibniz, J. Locke, Eastern scientists Al-Farabi, philosopher Ibn Sina, J. Balasagun and Kazakh thinkers A. Kunanboyev, Y. Oltinsarin, as well as foreign scientists R. Arnold, G. Vlumenstein, J. Raven, K. Rogers, I. V. Robert the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the concepts of "competence" are considered.

Various aspects of information in the field of education are found in the works of scientists of the CIS countries who are specially engaged in the issue of competence, professional competence, theory and methodology of competence in the teaching process: A.V. Khutorsky, I.A. Zimnya, V.A. Slastenin, V.S. Gershunsky, V. V. Kraevskiy, V.P. Bespalko, E.V. Bondarevskaya, M.V. Klarin, V. Mon, E.S. Po'lat, V.A. Sitarov, I.S. Yakimanskaya and others. The problems of unifying the ways of forming the communicative competence of future elementary school specialists through information technologies and determining their scientific and pedagogical foundations have not been fully resolved. However, the theoretical analysis of the above-mentioned works shows that in them the problems of forming the communicative competence of future primary school specialists through information technologies are comprehensively studied, proving that the problem we are considering has not yet found its solution.

In addition, there are contradictions between the fact that the theoretical foundations of the formation of the future specialist's communicative competence on the basis of information technologies have not been determined and there are no methodological guidelines for their practical implementation. In order to form the professional competence of future specialists through information technologies, it is necessary to acquire the first experience of informatization of education related to the educational system, to master pedagogical activities, and to form scientific-methodical experiences. This shows the need for the future elementary school teacher to work using special and professional knowledge and skills.

Research results

The position of multi-channel information flows refers to the provision of information relying on different channels of perception, such as sight and hearing. This can be achieved through

the use of texts, graphics, audio and video materials, drawings and tables. The principles of universalization and application of the content of communication information products are to create common methods of logic, interface, structure, to create a set of components of electronic materials for easy transition from one software product to another; as well as to focus on the external impact of materials, not on the form of its reception, but on its content.

The process of informatization of the educational process goes along with the second important process - modernization. One of the priority areas of modernization of education is the introduction of information technologies at all its stages. To increase the quality of the educational process in educational institutions and to connect to the global network of the Internet and local information sites that provide support for science in higher educational institutions, to provide higher education institutions with modern devices, tools and materials, the need for equipment is clearly indicated.

The expansion of the education and information space, the rapid growth of human knowledge - lead to a change in the attitude to the preparation of the future specialist, as well as the teacher for professional activity. Communicative competence, which forms the basis of professional competence, is such an indicator of preparation today. Information culture means acquisition of technologies and methods of working with information, skills of information search, presentation, processing and analysis. The information culture of the person is part of the general human culture necessary for the educational activity of the teacher and the student. Information culture is characterized by the existence of a complex of knowledge, skills, competences and traditional instructions for interaction with the information environment, which is observed during the implementation of special information processes. A good teacher must understand the need for information, be able to use it effectively to compare, disseminate, evaluate and make sound decisions.

Discussions

Information culture - interest in information activities, understanding of its important role in educational processes, conscious selection of information sources and mastering of algorithms for their processing, comprehensive use of traditional, electronic, online and other information resources, self-information carrier and as a distributor, is actively observed in information behavior. Due to the use of information technologies, changes in the educational process are carried out in two main directions: spatial and temporal changes of education, as well as changing the communicative nature of all subjects of the educational process.

Spatial change of education - the expansion of the educational space, the emergence of opportunities for remote interaction, the variability of educational directions. Therefore, there are additional requirements for the organization of a new space of the educational process: the availability of appropriate equipment, workplaces. In this regard, new requirements for the training of future specialists also appear: they create educational courses with the advice of a teacher or independently, organize their workplaces, orient to the flow of information, must have self-control. That is why the characteristics of the subject's educational activity: planning, forecasting, thinking abilities are very important. The temporary change in education is primarily related to the possibilities of direct and indirect exchange of various information at a distance.

The emergence of such opportunities creates a number of requirements for the timely organization of education using information technologies: taking into account the temporal limit

of information exchange, the need to properly plan communication time, taking into account psychological perception.

The influence of time in the execution of technical-indirect actions. As evidence for the spatio-temporal characteristics of the organization of educational processes, using information technologies, first of all, the possibilities of acquiring the knowledge and skills necessary for professional activity in different ways can be cited.

On the one hand, they allow the presentation of educational information with consistent, step-by-step control. On the other hand, students acquire the same knowledge and skills by studying these models, i.e. procedurally, thanks to process and event modeling tools. Information can be provided using tools such as electronic textbooks, test and control programs, reference books, educational databases, and educational videos. Processes can be modeled using simulation models, object-oriented environments, computer graphics and computer modeling, and laboratory practices, simulators, and game-based programs.

In this way, it will be possible to study phenomena and processes in the micro and macro world, internal complex technical and biological systems, and various physical, chemical, biological and social processes that occur at high and very low speeds. An example of this is the creation of an open education system that provides a unique educational path for each subject, the creation, development and improvement of a distance education system at various levels. At the same time, there was a need to solve the issue of creating an effective management system of information-methodical provision of education for the training of future specialists.

When analyzing information technologies, we rely on their classification. Classification can be made on several grounds: the way the information is presented, the language of the statement, and the opportunity to express an opinion. A combination of several methods helped to divide the broad classification of the studied technologies into two groups - audiovisual and computer. As an example of audiovisual technologies, we can cite various educational technologies, for example, the use of audio recordings.

Examples of visual technology are statistical images, silent film technology. Audiovisual technologies are offered in the form of educational electronic textbooks, video tapes, audio films, educational films and educational television. In terms of the spatial and temporal organization of the educational process, the video tape is prepared to divide any educational material into parts and components related to the performance of educational tasks. Thus, gradual, step-by-step, effective learning of the material is achieved and the possibility of self-study at a personal pace is provided. The first difference is that the educational content is presented in the form of complete, independent complexes (information blocks) that are a fund of information and methodological instructions for their study.

Thus, students work independently for a long time, form the skills of goal formation, planning, self-organization, self-control and self-evaluation. This allows to take into account their level of knowledge and skills, to see shortcomings and shortcomings. The possibility of individualizing the educational process is realized thanks to the use of educational and methodological complexes consisting of methodical instructions, forms for individual performance works.

The following levels (high, medium, low) of formation of communicative competence of future specialists through information technologies were determined. High level – student who has mastered the knowledge necessary for the formation of communicative competence of future

specialists on the basis of information technologies at a high level, creatively invented types of professional activities accordingly, self-confident, active, self-aware; a student who can self-organize and evaluate, has a unique character and is fully formed in its implementation in the practice of educational activities. Intermediate level – student who acquired sufficient knowledge necessary for the formation of communicative competence of future specialists with the help of information technologies, invented professional activity in accordance with it, applied it in the practice of educational activities, self-awareness; a student who is not fully formed, who is moderately active in self-organization and evaluation. Low level - a student who acquires knowledge of the basic subject to form the communicative competence of future specialists on the basis of information technology, strictly adheres to the given model, self-organization and evaluation, and cannot include it in the practice of educational activities

Conclusion

In short, in the formation of communicative competence of future specialists through information technologies, it is important to actively involve them in information activities, to independently master the tools and methods of information technologies. Dissemination of information technology tools and methods, specially organized information activities with future specialists are aimed at developing their personal experiences and increasing the level of formation of all competencies.

Global trends in the development of the higher education system lead to the emergence of a new environment - the information society. It was confirmed that the formation of communicative competence of future specialists through information technologies not only affects the quality of their education, but also creates conditions for increasing their opportunities to study at a higher educational institution.

For this, it is necessary to effectively organize the teaching process using information technology tools (new types of computers, telecommunications, virtual environment and multimedia technologies). We think that the formation of communicative competence of future specialists through information technologies, the implementation of teaching methods and technologies that sufficiently ensure their in-depth scientific training, pedagogical skills and the responsibility of combining innovation with special inquisitiveness is one of the important tasks from the point of view of today's basic requirements.

REFERENCES

1. The main reasons for the development and use of information and communication technologies in the field of education. 268-271 pp.
2. Nekotorye priznaki pedagogicheskix tekhnologiy// Gylymi zurnal Ízdenís. - 2012.- No. 3.- S.266-269.
3. The use of information and communication technologies is an important element of the formation of the career of vocational students// Khabarshy of the Qazaqstan pedagogical gylymdar academy. - 2014.- #3. 34-38 pp.
4. Modeling the communicative competence of a young class teacher based on information technologies//Gylymi zurnal Qazaqstan ustazy. 2014 .- #01(1). 5-10 pp.
5. Children's teacher training based on information technology// Education in Jog'ary education and the future of education - the main issues of pedagogic education and international education - a practical conference. - Abay atyndagy QazŪPU, 2012. pp. 281-284.

6. The role of artistic text in the education of the young generation // - "Improving the educational system in the context of social modernization" International scientific and practical conference.- Y. National Academy of Education named after Altynsarin. Astana, 2013. pp. 26-30.
7. The role of artistic text in the education of the young generation // - "Improving the educational system in the context of social modernization" International scientific and practical conference.- Y. National Academy of Education named after Altynsarin. Astana, 2013. pp. 26-30.
8. The usage of innovation technologies in formation of professional competence of the future specialists// 2 nd Cyprus International Conference on Educational Research.- 2013. 540-543 p.p.
9. Tolerance in the System of World – View Culture and Moral Development// Middle- East Journal of Scientific Research.- 2014. 802-804 p.p.